

THE CONCEPT OF "SERVICES": FROM THE POINT OF VIEW OF CIVIL DOCTRINE

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Abstract

This article analyzes the legal and economic aspects of the concept of service from the point of view of civil doctrine. The study examined the distinguishing features of services from work, their tangible and intangible results, as well as the specifics of service contracts. The author analyzed various scientific concepts and proposed a new approach to the concept of service. The article shows the relationship between the action as a service and the result expected from it.

Keywords: service, civil doctrine, contract, legal services, economic theory, material result, non-material result

Introduction

In modern legal science, the concept of service occupies an important place and is considered one of the central categories of civil law. However, there are various approaches to the legal nature and content of services in the scientific literature, which indicates insufficient study of this issue [1, 2].

The correct interpretation of the concept of service is of great importance in the practical application of law, particularly in the conclusion and execution of service contracts. Therefore, a deeper study of the theoretical foundations of this category is an urgent task [3].

The purpose of the research is to provide a comprehensive analysis of the concept of service from the point of view of civil doctrine and to reveal its legal and economic essence.

Analysis of scientific literature on the concept of service shows that there are two main approaches in this area: economic and legal. The first approach is aimed at studying the economic essence of service, the second - at studying its legal nature [4, 5].

Literature Review and Methodology

This phenomenon has been studied by various civilists at different periods, including T.P. Levshina, Yu.V. Romanets, L.I. and E.E. Shevchenko who studied various aspects of the concept of service [6, 7, 8]. Their research shows the organic connection of service with activity and its intangible character.

The works of V.A. Vaipan and D.I. Stepanov are devoted to the field of legal services, and they have contributed to revealing the specific features of services [9, 10].

The research employed comparative-legal, analytical and synthetic methods. Theoretical materials were analyzed and confirmed with practical examples.

Discussion

Distinguishing Features of Services from Works

In civil doctrine, when defining service, authors usually rely on features that distinguish it from works. The main feature is considered to be the organic connection of the service with the activity of providing it [13].

According to T.P. Levshina, service means certain actions or activities of the

performer. Some of these activities do not leave a material result, while others may produce a specific material result [6]. As an example, the author cites dental care - where there is a material result (a filling), while in therapeutic treatment there is none.

According to Levshina's concept, there is a common aspect inherent in all services: before the result, actions are performed that do not have material expression but constitute a unified whole with it. Based on this, she concludes that "in service provision, it is not the result itself that is 'sold', but the very action that leads to this result" [6].

Specificity of Service Results

The opinion of Yu.V. Romanets also deserves attention. According to him, "service provision may not lead to any result at all... due to the specificity of the obligation, this result is not fully guaranteed by the service being provided; even if the performer properly performed the contractual services, the expected result may not occur" [7].

When formulating this judgment, the author does not exclude the possibility of a positive result under certain conditions, but this can only indicate the "quality of services" [7].

According to the position of L.I. and E.E. Shevchenko, the subject of a legal services contract is not the performer's result, but the process that he carries out according to the client's assignment [8]. Although this process does not exclude the creation of some material object, for example, a draft contract or a lawsuit.

V.A. Vaipan, supporting this point of view, emphasizes that a lawyer's obligations under a contract for legal services for remuneration may include not only performing certain actions (for example, giving advice), but also providing the client with the results of these actions (written conclusion on a legal issue, document draft, etc.) [9].

As D.I. Stepanov emphasizes, in such contracts the essence of the service consists in providing advice to the client, and the material medium (paper) on which information (advice) is transmitted acts only as its form [10].

Specificity of Services in Various Fields

In many cases, the result of information services is the client's receipt of a material information carrier, while the result of audit services is a well-composed written conclusion by the auditor about the reliability of the financial and accounting activities of the company being audited [14].

As M.N. Maleina emphasizes, even if a positive result (for example, patient recovery) is included in the terms of a medical service contract, the issued document only confirms in writing the achieved result, but the result itself does not have material expression, since it consists of the volume of knowledge obtained [11].

E.G. Shablova's point of view that the method of expressing opinion (oral or written) does not change the economic essence of services is also appropriate [12].

Relationship Between Service and Result

Analysis of the presented scientific concepts shows that there is a relationship between action as a service and the goal pursued by such service - any "result". This result may approach contractor-type obligations, but is not exactly the same as them [15].

Despite such similarity, differences remain in the object, and these differences are determined by the specific features of the activity result. The general concept for service is the "action" (activity) of the service provider, which leads to a certain "result" that can be received by the service recipient at the level of sensations, perception, guarantees and can be expressed in writing to draw conclusions about quality [16].

Results

1. The legal and economic aspects of the concept of service do not deny each other, but on the contrary, complement each other and are interconnected.
2. The main feature of service is its organic connection with activity and its intangible (non-materialized) character.
3. In service provision, "it is not the result itself that is sold, but the very action that leads to this result."
4. There is an organic connection between action as a service and the result expected from it.
5. Service is the activity of a service provider that leads to a certain result perceived by the service recipient at the level of sensations, perception and guarantees.

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